
**SCHOOL-BASED RISK REDUCTION MANAGEMENT PRACTICES,
WORK EFFICIENCY AND SENSE OF SECURITY
AS EXPERIENCED IN PUBLIC
ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the relationship between the school – based risk reduction management practices and the work efficiency, and sense of security as experienced in public elementary school of Sariaya West District. The findings of this research may be utilized to establish a development program to upskill the school's risk reduction management practices. It is descriptive by design specifically utilized correlational research to examine the degree of association between variables. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and Regression analysis was used to identify the relationship between variables. The sampling technique used in the study for teachers, school heads, learners, parents, and community leaders was random sampling. The risk reduction management practices in terms of risk analysis and assessment, risk preparedness and risk transfer in selected public elementary schools are “always practiced” as perceived by the respondents. They perceived work in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy; diversity of learners & assessment and reporting; curriculum and planning; community linkages and professional engagement & personal growth and professional development; and plus factor shown that teachers are highly efficient. The respondents strongly agree that the indicators of sense of security in terms of existence, relatedness, and growth are “highly experienced”. There is significant relationship

between the school – based risk reduction management practices and work efficiency in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy; diversity of learners & assessment and reporting; curriculum and planning; community linkages and professional engagement & personal growth and professional development; and plus factor. There is significant relationship between the school – based risk reduction management practices and most of indicators of sense of security in terms of existence, relatedness, and growth. It implies that the school – based risk reduction management of public elementary schools of Sariaya West District influence the work efficiency of teachers and sense of security of teachers, school heads, and the learners.

Risk transfer is dominant of all the indicators of school-based risk reduction practices in the public elementary school set up. Plans and actions of the schools to divert hazards and risks to ease the consequences of a disaster is essential. It suggests contingency plans will also contribute and the school have the step – by – step procedures and nothing to worry about. With the help of internal and external stakeholders, the schools of Sariaya West District continuously survive on its operation in the presence of crisis.

Keywords: Risk Reduction Management, Work Efficiency, Sense of Security, Hazards

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process that supports the development of new information, skills, moral values, beliefs, habits, and learning. It is an opportunity to an individual to acquire new knowledge and skills through a system of learning phases. In many nations, anyone above a particular age must attend school. Teaching, learning, instruction, conversation, focused study, storytelling, and other techniques are all

used in education. A person's dynamic force is their education, which has a significant impact on their mental, emotional, social, physical, artistic, spiritual, and ethical growth. It enables someone to encounter a variety of things and use those things to build a fulfilling existence.

School is an educational institution that undertakes educational

operations. It is for students pursuing studies at defined levels, receiving instruction from teachers. It is the center of the formal education system where the learners go to acquire knowledge and skills, and provides the finest basic education for all students. (Republic Act No. 9155 Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001)

The school, as an institution, plays a role in the community in the development of responsible, responsive, and productive citizens. The school seeks to deliver quality education in a safe, inclusive, environmentally sustainable, and gender-friendly environment with the aid of teachers, administration, and stakeholders. According to Benitez (2015), a school is a safe school when it provides a learning environment wherein children's education, health, safety, and security are secured in both normal and disaster circumstances. It's also a group of students who are dedicated to building a safety culture, are aware of the dangers, and are prepared to respond to crises. Finally, it experiences minimal disruption during calamities, allowing the students to continue to study in a healthy setting.

To claim that the school is always safe is idealistic. Even when safety procedures are taken and the school administration ensures the school's security and stability, unforeseen events usually occur. Keeping schools safe not only ensures a secure learning environment for children. It also ensures that instructors and administrative staff are in a secure working environment. Every student's and teacher's school as their second home, and everyone's safety is important. Everyone plays a role in ensuring one another's safety. It is a difficult process, but working together can help.

With the present worldwide pandemic and the lessons learned from prior historical disasters, it is right time to reassess recent policies and practices in crisis response. What has transpired in the past has resulted in the current scenario. The present decision-making and actions can ensure the security and safety of the future.

Quezon Province, with its people endure challenges from the past years from the presence of the leftist movement New People's Army from 2002 & 2004 (in Sariaya), 2007(in Candelaria), 2021 (in

Bondoc Peninsula) and major natural calamities like landslides in Infanta (2004) & Typhoon Glenda (2014), was also affected by the spread of the Corona Virus Diseases – 2019 (Covid-19) that initiates the precautionary closure of major establishments especially the 1,156 schools with a total of 476,802 learners according to SDO-Quezon Planning Division(2020).

By issuing orders and memos that follow safety health protocols, special working arrangements, and standard operating procedures, the Department of Education continues to do its utmost to protect the safety of children, teachers, and non-teaching workers. Furthermore, public schools tried their best to protect the school's stability and safety, avoiding the greater risk that this epidemic may bring. The Department of Education, the government's leading educational agency, has implemented progressive limited face-to-face classes in low-risk areas as a step toward determining whether it is ready for nationwide implementation of face-to-face classes in the new normal and putting in place necessary safeguards to ensure the safety of teaching personnel, students, parents, and other stakeholders. Sariaya

West District took its part to support the current implementing rules and regulations given by the Central Office and Schools Division Office. From the skeletal work arrangements, following minimum health protocols, Covid-19 Response Committee, and School Disinfection Programs, the district supports the full implementation of programs to ensure the health safety and security of teaching and non-teaching personnel as well as the stakeholders. Following the recent memorandum, the District is able to conduct pilot testing of progressive limited face to face classes in majority of its schools after careful preparations of the school personnel and validations from the Division Office. Also, most of the activities conducted within the District is about disaster response during natural calamities. The main purpose of this study is to examine school-based risk reduction management practices as a whole in public elementary schools in the Sariaya West District, as well as their relationship to work efficiency and sense of security. The findings of this research may be used to create a framework for development program & policies and

upskilling current school-based risk reduction practices.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between the school – based risk reduction management practices and the work efficiency, and sense of security as experienced in public elementary schools of Sariaya West District. Specifically, this study sought to (1) identify the extent of practice of the school-based risk reduction management with regards to risk analysis and assessment, risk preparedness, and risk transfer ; (2) the perception of the respondents on work efficiency in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, diversity of learners & assessment and reporting, curriculum and planning, community linkages and professional engagement & personal growth and professional development, and plus factor; (3) describe the respondents' perception of their sense of security; (4) the correlation between the school – based risk reduction management practices and: work efficiency, and sense of security; and (5) identify the dominant indicator of school-

based risk reduction practices in public elementary school set – up.

METHODOLOGY

This study is descriptive by design as it utilized correlational research to examine the degree of association between or among the two or more important variables. The research concentrated on the current situation (what is). This is a type of research that focuses on the current conditions in a public elementary school, with an emphasis on school-based risk reduction management strategies and their link to work efficiency and sense of security of stakeholders. This investigation was conducted in 23 public elementary schools and communities in the Sariaya West District. . It was participated by three hundred seventy – eight (378) respondents in totality which includes one hundred seventy - five (175) teachers, fifteen (15) school heads, eighty-three (83) learners, eighty (80) parents, and thirty (30) community leaders.

The research questionnaire was translated into a google forms so that link will be sent to the teachers and school

principals. A hard copy of the questionnaire was also prepared for the learners, parents, and community leaders who were also the respondents of the study. It was all done with the guidance of the research consultant.

Before administering the surveys to the teachers, an authorization from the Schools Division Superintendent and Public Schools District Supervisor was requested. A letter of consent was also sent to the School Principals to seek for their assistance in data gathering. Consent of approval was sought to other stakeholders who were also respondents of this study. Following approval, sufficient copies of the questionnaires were printed and handed to the respondents personally.

A copy of the questionnaire was created digitally and to be sent to the

respondents who able to use google forms by the researcher. To guarantee that the surveys will be successfully retrieved, the aid of the school officials was requested. The completed questionnaire was collected, tabulated, and enclosed before being sent to the statistician for statistical analysis.

To determine the significant relationship of the risk reduction management practices with work efficiency, and sense of security, Pearson Product- Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.01 level of confidence was employed. To determine the predictability as affected by risk reduction management practices, work efficiency, and sense of security, regression analysis was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Risk Reduction Management Practices as Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Indicators	Internal Stakeholder			External Stakeholder		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
Risk Analysis and Assessment	3.66	0.42	AP	3.77	0.43	AP
Risk Preparedness	3.65	0.41	AP	3.73	0.34	AP
Risk Transfer	3.67	0.40	AP	3.79	0.46	AP
Over All	3.66	0.41	AP	3.76	0.41	AP

Scale: 3.50 – 4.00 Always Practiced (AP) 1.50 – 2.49 Seldom Practiced (SP)
2.50 – 3.49 Often Practiced (OP) 1.00 – 1.49 Never Practiced (NP)

Table 1. Summary on Risk Reduction Management Practices as Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Summary of risk reduction management practices experienced in selected public elementary schools is shown in Table 1. Overall mean shows that they are always practiced. It suggests that the schools from Sariaya West District are able to divert risk and

hazards through its contingency plans and actions. Even if it is always practiced, the degree of actual preparations that every school is doing is differ from one another. But there are different situations in various schools on how they prepare themselves. It is also show that the schools in Sariaya West District is on its way to improved its risk preparedness efforts.

2. Work Efficiency Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Indicators	Internal Stakeholder			External Stakeholder		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.67	0.50	HE	3.73	0.52	HE
Diversity of Learners & Assessment and Reporting	3.69	0.41	HE	3.73	0.43	HE
Curriculum Planning	3.71	0.40	HE	3.77	0.34	HE
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.75	0.36	HE	3.75	0.34	HE
Plus Factor	3.64	0.47	HE	3.71	0.41	HE
Overall	3.69	0.43	HE	3.74	0.41	HE

Scale: 3.50 – 4.00 Highly Efficient (HE) 1.50 – 2.49 Moderately Efficient (ME)
2.50 – 3.49 Efficient (E) 1.00 – 1.49 Slightly Efficient (SE)

Table 2. Summary on Work Efficiency Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Table 2 displays the summary on work efficiency experienced in selected public elementary schools. Based on the overall mean, all indicators shown that teachers are highly efficient. The hardwork of the teachers from Sariaya West Districts to cultivate their professional engagement, personal growth, and professional development resulted better as well as their connections and linkages with

community. Their efforts to prepare learning experiences that is suited for every pupil to develop their knowledge and skills. This suggest that curriculum planning they are doing is on the right track. The program they offering to the learners are useful. Both stakeholder views that teachers may continue to enhance their knowledge and capabilities by improving their plus factor which is also essential for their personal and professional development.

3. Sense of Security Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Indicators	Internal Stakeholder			External Stakeholder		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	SV
Existence	3.48	0.41	E	3.44	0.45	E
Relatedness	3.64	0.40	HE	3.76	0.31	HE
Growth	3.72	0.41	HE	3.79	0.34	HE
Over All	3.61	0.41	HE	3.66	0.37	HE

Scale: 3.50 – 4.00 Highly Experienced (HE) 1.50 – 2.49 Moderately Experienced (ME)
2.50 – 3.49 Experienced (E) 1.00 – 1.49 Slightly Experienced (SE)

Table 3. Summary of Sense of Security Experienced in Public Elementary Schools

Summary on sense of security experienced in selected public elementary schools is presented in Table 3. The respondents agree to the indicators that they are highly experienced. It implies that the respondents are open to the opportunities to grow and develop. They

exercise their capabilities to be mature and reach their goals. Most of the respondents are continuously seeking ways on how to grow and motivates self to continue in spite of challenges they are going through. They have the courage to continue and be more flexible, open-minded, and positive in every situation.

On the other hand, in terms of Existence, the respondents agree with indicators, it appears some of the respondents take a deeper thinking on how they define their way of living. World

health crisis made everyone realized what are the things that matter most. The difference between needs and wants. It also implicates that some of the respondents are contended on the way how they live. Others are not fully satisfied especially to those experienced difficulty in receiving aid in the most needed time especially during COVID-19 Surge and Community Lockdowns.

4. Correlation of School – Based Risk Reduction Management Practices, With Work Efficiency and Sense of Security

		Work Efficiency					Sense of Security		
		CKP	DLAR	CP	CLPEPG	PF	EXIS	RELATED	GROWTH
Risk Analysis and Assessment	HI	.554**	.548**	.612**	.608**	.481**	.381**	.548**	.526**
	VA	.692**	.654**	.706**	.662**	.592**	.432**	.544**	.567**
	IA	.674**	.658**	.726**	.712**	.589**	.476**	.559**	.592**
Risk Preparedness	CO	.597**	.552**	.601**	.668**	.563**	.453**	.505**	.488**
	TPE	.694**	.664**	.691**	.711**	.659**	.488**	.550**	.550**
	S	.580**	.547**	.542**	.561**	.536**	.490**	.470**	.450**
	PI	.728**	.710**	.750**	.687**	.608**	.503**	.622**	.626**
	EI	.706**	.676**	.716**	.725**	.600**	.481**	.565**	.568**
Risk Transfer	AL	.751**	.686**	.712**	.723**	.631**	.500**	.593**	.629**
	O	.732**	.695**	.754**	.754**	.653**	.480**	.607**	.617**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).
 Scale: -.35 to +.35 Weak Correlation + .35 to +.65 Moderate Correlation + .65 to + 1 Strong Correlation
 -.35 to -.65 Moderate Correlation -.65 to - 1 Strong Correlation

- Legend:
- HI – Hazard Identification
 - VA – Vulnerability Assessment
 - IA – Impact Analysis
 - CO – Community Organizing
 - TPE – Training, Planning & Equipping
 - S – Stockpiling
 - PI – Public Information
 - EI – Education Initiatives
 - AL – Accountability and Liability
 - O – Outsourcing
 - CKP – Content, Knowledge, and Pedagogy
 - DLAR – Diversity of Learners and Assessment & Reporting
 - CP – Curriculum Planning
 - CLPEPG - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development
 - PF – Plus Factor
 - EXIS - Existence
 - RELATED - Relatedness
 - GROWTH - Growth

Table 4.1 Correlation of School – Based Risk Reduction Management Practices, With Work Efficiency and Sense of Security as Perceived by Internal Stakeholders

Table 4.1 displays the correlation of school – based risk reduction management practices with work efficiency and sense of security as perceived by internal stakeholder. The table reveals that all the indicators of school – based risk reduction management practices are significantly related to work efficiency and sense of security. It implies that the school – based risk reduction management of selected public elementary schools of Sariaya West District influence the work efficiency of teachers and sense of security of teachers, school heads, and the learners. Through the preliminary measures of the schools to identify the possible hazards that may affect the school operations, school personnel are able to prepare themselves. They are able to do their duties and responsibilities at school. Moreover, they are equipping themselves through training and workshops for them to be ready. Continuous practice of Fire Drill, Earthquake Drill, and other safety drill helps the school to be familiarize on the things they need to do. The organization

of School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Team also give assistance in planning, implementing, and assessing the contingency plans. With the given support and resources from school, school personnel can work wisely and efficiently. Recognizing their school duties and responsibilities, school personnel can handle different situations.

Furthermore, the strategies that a school is implementing to ensure the safety and security of the schools affects the way the teachers will perform and their feeling of safety and security increases. The safer they feel within their environment, the better they will perform their duties and responsibilities and there are contended with their sense of security. Moreover, as the risk reduction management practices are regularly done in schools, internal stakeholders do not need to worry and can focus to their works and achievements. They confidently work and perform their best. School personnel saves time and effort at work and continuously achieving the school goals in terms of safety and security.

		Work Efficiency					Sense of Security		
		CKP	DLAR	CP	CLPEPG	PF	EXIS	RELATED	GROWTH
Risk Analysis and Assessment	HI	.389**	.432**	.637**	.534**	.560**	.237*	.477**	.542**
	VA	.241*	.275**	.316**	.307**	.292**	.014	.197*	.288**
	IA	.461**	.519**	.691**	.646**	.697**	.296**	.532**	.517**
Risk Preparedness	CO	.433**	.456**	.671**	.622**	.689**	.293**	.506**	.511**
	TPE	.570**	.548**	.695**	.692**	.678**	.254**	.509**	.530**
	S	.506**	.580**	.699**	.627**	.549**	.147	.394**	.375**
	PI	.530**	.589**	.827**	.704**	.732**	.305**	.595**	.585**
	EI	.563**	.635**	.817**	.750**	.643**	.226*	.515**	.490**
Risk Transfer	AL	.675**	.688**	.793**	.792**	.836**	.309**	.592**	.567**
	O	.397**	.394**	.429**	.430**	.453**	.189*	.380**	.352**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Scale: -.35 to +.35 Weak Correlation +.35 to +.65 Moderate Correlation +.65 to +1 Strong Correlation
-.35 to -.65 Moderate Correlation -.65 to -1 Strong Correlation

Legend:

HI – Hazard Identification

VA – Vulnerability Assessment

IA – Impact Analysis

CO – Community Organizing

TPE – Training, Planning & Equipping

S – Stockpiling

PI – Public Information

EI – Education Initiatives

AL – Accountability and Liability

O – Outsourcing

CKP – Content, Knowledge, and Pedagogy

DLAR – Diversity of Learners and Assessment & Reporting

CP – Curriculum Planning

CLPEPG – Community Linkages and Professional Engagement & Personal Growth and Professional Development

PF – Plus Factor

EXIS – Existence

RELATED – Relatedness

GROWTH – Growth

Table 4.2 Correlation of School – Based Risk Reduction Management Practices, With Work Efficiency and Sense of Security as Perceived by External Stakeholders

Table 4.2 presents correlation of school – based risk reduction management practices, with work efficiency and sense of security as perceived by external stakeholder. The table reveals that majority of the indicators of school-based reduction management are significantly related to work efficiency and sense of security. It suggests that parents and community leaders believe that the teachers are work efficient as the school practiced risk reduction management. They perceived that the school itself do its part to ensure safety and security. The school measures done for hazard mapping is

implemented. With the support of the community through Brigada Eskwela, the school building and facilities itself is being prepared and maintenance for the benefit of the stakeholders. With the generous support from the community, public schools in Sariaya West District continues its operation in spite of challenges that is taking place. Parents and Community Leaders believe that their child that is going to school are safe and secure, thus the teachers can be competent at work which will also reflects to school’s performance. In addition, school – based risk reduction management is significantly related to

sense of security in terms of relatedness and growth. It implies that the parents and community leaders give importance and appreciate the best practices that the school is doing especially when it comes to safety and security. They are also affected to what procedures, rules, and regulations of the schools as they support their child's education and support the programs of the school.

However, the sense of security in terms of existence have weak correlation with the school – based reduction management practices. It may suggest that it does not directly affect the way of living of the external stakeholder. As the head of their own family, they made major decisions that affects the household. Though there are present practices that can be adopted, majority of the family follows what is convenient to them. They may not practice hazard mapping at home, risk preparedness measures, managing the resources well or even recognizing the duties and responsibilities of each family member. They may believe that school – based risk reduction management is for schools only and not applicable at home. Parents and community leaders are independent on how they will live their life. Despite of

that, the school is always there and willing to help and to educate the community. Proper information and communication to the community surrounding the school is needed.

Vulnerability Assessment also shows weak correlation as perceived by the External Stakeholders. It implies that the experiences from school is far different on what is happening at home. Safety concerns in schools is different from the safety concerns at home. They are different levels of problems and concerns that the external stakeholders experienced especially in terms of safety and security. There are vulnerabilities happening at home that cannot be controlled by internal stakeholders. The world health crisis affects the point of view of the parents and community leaders. The school operations despite of the crisis is also affected. Whether the school is ready or not in the face of current challenges, the primarily concerns of the parents and community leaders are survival and looking forward for a better year to come. Continuing their child's education is one of the concerns they are experiencing at present.

5. Regression Analysis of Work Efficiency and Sense of Security Based on School-Based Risk Reduction Management Practices

Table 5.1 Regression of Work Efficiency Based on School – Based Risk Reduction Management Practices

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	0.585	0.118		4.944	0.000
Risk Transfer	0.388	0.054	0.412	7.221	0.000
Risk Preparedness	0.276	0.068	0.270	4.032	0.000
Risk Analysis and Assessment	0.198	0.052	0.199	3.785	0.000
Type of Stakeholders	-0.048	0.024	-0.060	-1.986	0.048

R = .819, R² = .670, Adj R² = .667, F (4, 373) = 189.558, p = .000

Table 26 presents the regression of work efficiency based on school – based risk reduction practices. A multiple regression was run to predict work efficiency from the school-based risk reduction practices such as risk analysis and assessment, risk preparedness, and risk transfer, and the type of stakeholders. All these variables significantly predict the work efficiency and explained 67% of the variance of the work efficiency. This shows that the school-based risk reduction practices have positive effect on the work efficiency and while being internal stakeholder reduces the predicted work efficiency. It suggests that when it is safe and secure, the performance works at its best. School practices measures in

connection with risk reduction management. Teachers and other school personnel are able to work without worries and hesitation. They are able to perform efficiently and reach goals and objectives. With a working school personnel efficiently, school operations continue to serve and uphold education of the surrounding community.

In the midst of worldwide health crisis, it tests the capacity of the schools to continue in spite of danger that is present. The result that being internal stakeholder reduces the predicted work efficiency. It implies that when a school never practicing or low in practicing risk reduction management there is a possibility that the school may have low

performing personnel to the school – based risk reduction management practices. The degree of their compliance to the practice affects their point of view in spite of regular implementation. With the gradual start of Progressive Limited Face-to-Face Classes, teachers and learners as well as schools are in the

period of adjustment. School Safety Protocols are established and continuous monitoring for its compliance is a must. Later on, the teachers, school heads, and learners will become accustomed. This is the start where the teachers and schools will perform on their best continuously.

Table 5.2 Regression of Sense of Security Based on School-Based Risk Reduction Management Practices

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.212	0.146		8.300	0.000
Risk Transfer	0.279	0.067	0.313	4.190	0.000
Risk Preparedness	0.198	0.065	0.210	3.047	0.002
Risk Analysis and Assessment	0.176	0.085	0.182	2.076	0.039

$R = .657, R^2 = .431, \text{Adj } R^2 = .427, F(3, 374) = 94.490, p = .000$

Table 5.2 presents the regression of sense of security based on school-based risk reduction practices. A multiple regression was run to predict sense of security from the school-based risk reduction practices such as risk analysis and assessment, risk preparedness, and risk transfer, and the type of stakeholders. All school-based risk reduction practices significantly predict the sense of security and explained 43% of its variance.

This shows that the school-based risk reduction practices have positive

effect on the sense of security. It implies that school-based risk reduction practices affect sense of security of every individual that enters and exits the schools in Sariaya West District. Doing these practices, teachers are confident to go to school to teach their students and do related works. The school heads are assured that things will go through smoothly and the school is ready to face challenges. Learners are positive that they will learn new things from school. Parents and community leaders are assured that their child is safe and secure when they are in school. With the current

world health crisis, the primary concern is safety and security. Discouragements and doubts are also present to different individuals and affect their point of view. Despite of that, following the minimum health and safety protocols as well as implementing the school safety assessment tool, the schools are improving and strengthening its safety and security measures one paced at a time.

On the other hand, the risk transfer has the largest effect on the sense of security. Plans and actions of the schools to divert hazards and risks to ease the consequences of a disaster is essential. It suggests contingency plans

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. There is significant relationship between the school – based risk reduction management and work efficiency. It is also revealed that being internal stakeholders reduces the predicted work efficiency.
2. There is significant relationship between the school – based risk

will also contribute and the school have the step – by – step procedures and nothing to worry about. With the help of internal and external stakeholders, the schools of Sariaya West District continuously survive on its operation in the presence of crisis. With the competent school personnel and leadership of its administrators, schools manage and upskill itself. Learning the duties and responsibilities of one another can help, too. It also means that being a teacher, school heads, learners, parents or community leaders, plans for tomorrow reflects readiness on what may happen. Everyone is assertive that everything is under control.

reduction management practices and sense of security as experienced except the indicator of vulnerability assessment and existence by public elementary school. External Stakeholders are still concern to the safety and security procedures and practices of the school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Schools may continue to practice the risk reduction management and focus its effort to risk preparedness.
2. Schools may continue its efforts to tap generous donors for continue its support the school and help indigent students.
3. Administrators may provide trainings and activities to strengthen the risk reduction management of the schools and the district.
4. School heads may create developmental program that is suited to their respective schools aligned to risk reduction management practices.
5. Teachers may continue strengthen their capacity and

abilities through trainings, workshops, chairmanships, and coordinators to maintain its high efficiency in work.

6. A replication of this study can be done to other district, may use mixed – method to gather information from internal stakeholders and / or external stakeholders and may conduct further study about the impact of natural or human – induced disaster in school operations and to the capacity of the school to response, mitigate, and recover.
7. A further study may be conducted to gather information to external stakeholders about risk reduction management and the sense of mechanism: awareness, readiness, and implementation.

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